

AttenGait: gait recognition with attention and rich modalities

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Abstract

Current gait recognition systems employ different types of manual attention mechanisms, like horizontal cropping of the input data to guide the training process and extract useful gait signatures for people identification. Typically, these techniques are applied using silhouettes as input, which limits the learning capabilities of the models. Thus, due to the limited information provided by silhouettes, state-of-the-art gait recognition approaches must use very simple and manually designed mechanisms, in contrast to approaches proposed for other topics such as action recognition. To tackle this problem, we propose AttenGait, a novel model for gait recognition equipped with trainable attention mechanisms that automatically discover interesting areas of the input data. AttenGait can be used with any kind of informative modalities, such as optical flow, obtaining state-of-the-art results thanks to the richer information contained in those modalities. We evaluate AttenGait on two public datasets for gait recognition: CASIA-B and GREW; improving the previous state-of-the-art results on them, obtain-

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ing 95.8% and 70.7% average accuracy, respectively. *Code will be available at <https://github.com/fmcp/attengait>.*

Keywords: Gait, optical flow, deep learning, attention, biometrics.

1. Introduction

Gait refers to the walking style of a person. It can be considered a biometric feature that, like fingerprints or iris, can be used to identify people by the way they walk. In contrast to fingerprint- or iris-based recognition approaches, gait recognition is considered non-invasive since it is performed at a distance and does not require the cooperation of the subject that has to be identified. Therefore, great effort has been put into gait recognition [1] in the last years. Although there exist approaches using different input modalities, such as optical flow [2], inertial sensors [3], gray images [4], or even multiple modalities at the same time [5], most of the recent methods rely on silhouettes [6, 7, 8, 9]. This decision goes against the intuition of other computer vision problems that try to use the richest possible inputs [10, 11]. The gait recognition community supporting the use of silhouettes justify them for privacy reasons and in order to force models to learn from gait trait and not from textures (*i.e.* visual appearance) obtained from clothing, for example. Recent gait recognition approaches [6, 7, 9] based on silhouettes propose neural models with a reduced number of parameters but producing a huge number of activations to represent the same input in many different ways. Thus, *are these models really learning to identify people by focusing on the subtle patterns of the gait? or just learning to produce many repetitive features?* In our humble opinion, this is a way to get around the enormous limitation imposed by silhouettes since data only contains binary values and, in addition, their quality highly depends on the silhouette extractor, as we show in Sec. 4. Nevertheless, in a real-life scenario

where the background changes over time, this decision gives rise to the following research questions: *what would be the performance of silhouette-based models if the silhouette extractor failed?* or even thinking further, *could another modality be used?* Let us imagine a real-life environment, which is far from the ideal laboratory conditions seen in common gait recognition datasets [12, 13, 14], where we need to identify people by their way of walking. *Will a model be penalized for achieving high accuracy using non-silhouette modalities, and if so, what might be the motivation behind this decision?* One could think about privacy since the dataset is distributed with raw videos where subjects can be easily identified or the information codified in model weights could be employed to recover subject-sensitive data [15]. Another problem of raw videos is the domain shift from gait recognition to person re-identification since models could focus on unrelated details (*i.e.* faces, textures, clothes, etc.) to the gait. While we acknowledge these limitations, another kind of data such as optical flow can be used since it guarantees subject anonymity by removing appearance details but having data much richer than silhouettes.

To answer all those questions, this paper proposes AttenGait, an attention network for gait recognition that can use rich input data such as optical flow. In addition, we provide thorough experimentation to justify using other modalities instead of the traditional silhouettes and, hopefully, inspire the gait recognition community to think about using different input data. In contrast to previous works that rely just on traditional 2D/3D CNN models [6, 7, 9], AttenGait is inspired by Transformers [16, 11] and their attention mechanism to focus along time on essential regions of the body from a gait recognition perspective, as shown in Fig. 1. Therefore, the model should be able to abstract from items, such as bags or cloth-

Figure 1: **Overview.** AttenGait is a novel architecture that receives a sequence of optical flow maps derived from a walking person to generate a gait signature, considering the importance of the different regions of the input data. L , w , and h represent the number of frames, width, and height of the input sample, respectively.

ing, and pay more attention to other elements, such as arms or legs swinging during walking. To achieve this goal, we propose three different attention blocks as shown in Fig. 2: an Attention conv to discover essential areas without considering the temporal information, a Spatial Attention HPP takes horizontal crops of the input data that are weighted according to their spatial importance, and a Temporal Attention HPP that locates important horizontal regions according to their temporal information. As pointed out in previous works on video transformers [11], these kinds of models require a massive amount of training data to achieve good performance. In our case, since all public datasets are relatively small compared to image or action recognition datasets, we have to escape from silhouettes and use richer input data such as optical flow. This way, our model receives more information with a wider range of values instead of just binary images, which allows us to train it better.

The main contributions of this paper can be summarized in: (i) a novel gait recognition model equipped with three novel trainable attention mechanisms that

automatically learn to focus on essential regions of the input data; *(ii)* a flexible model in terms of input data that is able to handle different visual modalities; *(iii)* an experimental study to measure the impact of the different modalities on the final accuracy of the model; and, *(iv)* state-of-the-art results for CASIA-B and GREW using optical flow as input data.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. We start by reviewing related work in Sec. 2. Then, Sec. 3 explains the proposed approach. Sec. 4 contains the experiments and results. Finally, we present the conclusions in Sec. 5.

2. Related work

Gait recognition. The most commonly used approaches in the literature involve silhouette-based methods [6, 7, 8, 9, 17]. GEI [18] represents one of the most straightforward approaches since the whole video sequence is summarized into a single frame containing spatio-temporal information. However, it is sensitive to variations in real-world scenarios. GaitSet [6] uses a random stack of silhouettes where each frame is handled independently to extract features that are finally combined and fed into a Horizontal Pyramid Pooling (HPP) module that extracts non-learned features from 62 splits from the same input. A different approach called GaitPart is presented in [7], where a novel part-based model extracts features from horizontal splits of intermediate convolutional activations. Similarly to [6], each frame is handled independently to build features that are combined and fed into an HPP module. GLN [8] concatenates intermediate convolutional activations to build a huge descriptor that reinforces the discrimination capabilities of the model. To reduce the dimensionality of the output, the authors of this approach propose a compression module attached to the model’s end. Finally,

GaitGL [9], which is the current state-of-the-art approach, borrows the idea of split convolutions from [7] and applies it to 3D convolutions together with a simplified version of the HPP proposed in [6]. However, silhouette-based approaches can be subject to drastic variations, such as changes in body shape, clothing, illumination, dynamic backgrounds, or other factors. Other works rely on alternative sensors like accelerometer [3, 19] or wave-sensors [20]. Skeleton-based systems have also been employed as an alternative to silhouette- and sensor-based systems thanks to new gait datasets that provide skeleton information [21, 14]. However, the results obtained are still far from the other visual modalities like silhouettes. For example, Liao *et al.* [22] propose a CNN model to deal with 3D joint information. Li *et al.* [23] go a step forward and propose a joint model that computes silhouette and skeleton information together with the identity of the subjects using that derived information from RGB input data. Teepe *et al.* [24] decompose the skeleton movement into three components: joints, bones and velocities, which are fed into a multibranch CNN to predict the identity of the subjects. And, Wang *et al.* [25] propose a transformer-based approach with a new attention block using skeletons as input. Recently, some approaches [26, 27] have been proposed using a 3D mesh representation, which can be seen as a combination of silhouettes with 3D pose information to produce a richer representation. This way, it includes binary values and information about the different body parts and their spatial location. Optical flow maps have also been proposed to represent gait [28]. This representation is computationally easy to calculate, although its precision depends on the speed of the object, a non-critical fact in gait recognition. A logical extension of all previous approaches that focus on a single kind of input data is the use of multimodal models. This kind of methods use data from different sources or

sensors. For example, Kumar *et al.* [29] use data from multiple inertial sensors to obtain a 3D-skeleton representation accompanied by video images. Castro *et al.* [5] builds a CNN model that jointly uses optical flow, depth, and gray images to improve the global gait accuracy of the model. UGaitNet [30] proposes a robust multimodal approach against missing modalities. This way, when an input modality is missed due to external circumstances, the model can produce robust results with the rest of modalities. Liang *et al.* [31] propose a two-staged multimodal approach that obtains silhouettes from RGB information to feed them to a gait recognition model that identifies the subjects. GaitCopy [4] uses a teacher-student methodology to train a student model that uses gray images to mimic the behavior of a master model trained with optical flow.

Attention mechanisms. Attention mechanisms [32] began to gain importance with the advent of vision transformers (ViT) [16], which is a rising topic in the computer vision field since the first adaptation from language processing to image processing. After that first implementation, several approaches have proposed improvements to the original ViT [16], *e.g.*, using a teacher-student scheme to help the training process [33], a better tokenization scheme to produce more robust crops from the input data [34], using a hierarchical scheme of tokens to obtain richer local information [35, 36], or adding convolutions to the attention mechanism [37, 10] to the best of both worlds.

However, in the field of gait recognition, only a few works use attention mechanisms or transformers. For example, [38] uses a simple attention mechanism by manually splitting the input samples into horizontal crops. A further step is proposed in [39], where horizontal and vertical crops are used to improve the learning capabilities of the model. In [40], its authors propose a simple multi-

modal approach by attaching two transformers blocks with self-attention at the end of a traditional CNN architecture. A basic gait recognition approach applying a ViT transformer is presented in [41]. However, its results are not comparable with other approaches since a different data split is used in their experiments. A more elaborated approach is presented in [42], where authors use an initial set of traditional convolutions and HPP to produce a set of gait features fed into a ViT-inspired transformer. Cui *et al.* [43] proposes a multimodal approach using two well-known encoders for silhouettes [9] and pose information [44] together with two attention modules that fuse both modalities. Fan *et al.* [45] propose a novel model combining convolutional blocks with transformers blocks at the end.

In this work, we propose a novel approach, AttenGait, inspired by transformers and their cropping and attention mechanisms. Our attention mechanism weights feature regions according to their importance for the gait recognition task. Moreover, unlike previous state-of-the-art approaches, AttenGait uses richer information, like optical flow, to learn better gait signatures than binary silhouettes.

3. Proposed model

We propose AttenGait which is a network for gait recognition using a trainable attention mechanism different from traditional self-attention [32]. Our model employs a cropping and attention mechanism to build robust gait signatures using rich data from modalities such as optical flow in contrast to traditional silhouettes. This way, these modalities allow to design and apply a more complex model than traditional architectures designed for silhouettes. In this section, we first motivate AttenGait, then we describe its architecture (Sec. 3.1) and, finally, we comment on the training and testing procedures (Sec. 3.2 and Sec. 3.3).

Figure 2: **AttenGait: gait recognition model equipped with trainable attention mechanisms to focus on important regions of the input data.** Sequences of L consecutive frames of $64 \times 64 \times C$ pixels are fed into a main branch to extract general spatio-temporal features. Then, two branches extract temporal features and spatio-temporal features. After concatenating each branch features (\oplus operation), a common branch builds the final spatio-temporal gait signatures. ‘ACx’ refers to Attention Convs, ‘2D-Cx’ and ‘3D-Cx’ refers to 2D and 3D convolutions, respectively, and ‘AM’ refers to the Attention Mask. Finally, ‘FCx’ refers to dense layers. Activations shape is included after each block.

Motivation. In the last years, state-of-the-art gait recognition approaches [6, 7, 9] that obtain the best results for different datasets use silhouettes as input and produce very long gait signatures (from 4k to 15k dimensions). Although some approximations [8, 46] have been proposed to solve these problems, their results are worse than the state-of-the-art methods. Therefore, we introduce AttenGait, an artificial neural network equipped with cropping and attention mechanisms that can generate shorter and more discriminative gait signatures from richer modalities (e.g. optical flow or gray images, although not limited to them).

3.1. *AttenGait*

In this section, we describe the input data, the different components of the model, and the training and testing processes used in our approach.

3.1.1. *Input data*

The input of our model is a stack of L consecutive frames of a given modality, where the subjects are cropped along the horizontal axis of the scene to normalize the input data as done in previous works [6, 7, 9]. This normalization is applied since each subject has its walking speed and position in the scene, which produces different horizontal displacements along the L stacked frames. Thus, the model should learn to isolate discriminative walking features to identify subjects even though they could appear in very different horizontal positions along the scene. To help the training process of our model, we align the cropped L frames in such a way that the body of the subject is x -located in the middle of all frames, guaranteeing similar positions of the subjects in the scene independently of the viewpoint and the walking speed.

3.1.2. *Architecture*

AttenGait, illustrated in Fig. 2, takes as input a sample composed of L consecutive frames of a given modality and returns the predicted identity of the person appearing in the given sample. The proposed architecture consists of a *main branch* (in blue) composed of several Attention Conv blocks to produce general spatio-temporal features considering the importance of each spatial region of the input sample. Then, two parallel branches extract spatial features and temporal features, respectively, using specific attention blocks. On the one hand, the *Spatial Attention HPP*, represented in green in Fig. 2, begins summarizing the temporal

Figure 3: **Attention Mask.** For a given input data, N optical flow crops are extracted and fed into the Attention Mask kernel. This kernel weights (\odot operation) each crop with a learned parameter and normalize the output. Finally, all crops are merged to build the output with the shape of the input data.

information directly from the activations of the *main branch* and uses 2D convolutions to obtain spatial features. On the other hand, the *Temporal Attention HPP* (shown in orange) computes spatio-temporal features using 3D convolutions. In this way, each branch produces different features obtained with different layers and focuses on further details of the walking pattern. Finally, a *common branch* (in purple) receives and concatenates the features from both branches. Then, several dense layers and attention masks produce the final gait signatures to predict the subject identities. Note that all implementation details about the architecture are included in Sec. 4.2.

3.1.3. Attention mechanisms

Since the data preprocessing (Sec. 3.1.1) places the subjects in the middle of the frame, we can design attention mechanisms to take advantage of this normalized position. This way, those mechanisms must find important spatial regions independently of the viewpoint and shape of the subjects. The key elements of AttenGait, shown in Fig. 2, are the three different attention blocks designed to identify important regions of the input data, forcing the model to pay more attention to those critical areas.

The *Attention Conv* (blue block in Fig. 2) discovers important areas without considering the temporal information; thus, it must find important regions for all frames. The *Spatial Attention HPP* (green block in Fig. 2) takes horizontal crops of the input data that are weighted according to their spatial importance. Finally, the *Temporal Attention HPP* (red block in Fig. 2) locates important horizontal regions according to their temporal information. Thus, each block focuses on different attributes, but all have the same goal: discovering the critical information to maximize recognition accuracy.

Note that all attention blocks use an attention mask whose computation is shown in Eq. 1, where N is the number of extracted regions and A is the attention mask composed of a set of trainable weights, one per extracted region.

$$AM = softmax\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}A\right) \quad (1)$$

A graphical overview of the Attention Mask operation is provided in Fig. 3. Below, we provide further details regarding the proposed attention blocks.

Therefore, in contrast to self-attention mechanisms, our attention kernel does not require query, key and value matrices. It uses masked local attention simplifying the computation between tokens since subjects are located in the middle of the

image. Moreover, once the attention is computed, the extracted tokens are placed again in their corresponding position of the input. This way, positional information is not required. Thus, our attention mechanism is simpler and faster since gait recognition specificities allow to simplify the attention computation.

Attention Conv. It comprises two trainable components: the Attention Mask and a 2D convolution. On the one hand, the Attention Mask, which is shown in Fig. 3 and described in (Eq. 1), extracts regions from the input data following a dense grid pattern of $k_w \times k_h$ pixels, where k_w and k_h are the width and height of the region, respectively. This way, for a given input data whose shape is $w \times h$, the Attention Mask extracts $N = \text{ceil}(\frac{w}{k_w}) \cdot \text{ceil}(\frac{h}{k_h})$ regions. If w or h are not divisible by k_w or k_h , respectively, smaller regions than $k_w \times k_h$ are extracted to allow the model to learn in those small regions. Note that the extracted regions also contain the same number of frames and channels as the input data to the layer, but for better understanding reasons, we simplified the notation removing the axes containing temporal information and channels. Thus, the complete shape of an extracted region is $f \times k_w \times k_h \times c$, where f is the number of frames and c is the number of input data channels. Afterwards, each region is repositioned to its original input location and assigned a weight based on a learned parameter, which signifies the importance or attention that the model should attribute to that specific part of the input data. Finally, the second trainable component is a 2D convolution applied to the attention map to extract features, considering each region’s importance and the local information within regions. To better understand the attention mechanism, Eq. 2 describes, from a simplified mathematical viewpoint, the kernel operations.

$$AC(x) = \text{conv2D}(AM_i \cdot x_i), \quad 1 \leq i \leq N \quad (2)$$

where x is the input data, N is the number of extracted regions and AM_i is the attention mask for a given region x_i .

Spatial Attention HPP. We propose a fully trainable Horizontal Pyramid Pooling (HPP) [6] combined with an attention mechanism. Traditional HPP layers extract constant pyramidal regions that are compressed using reduction operations, like maximum or average over a given axis. In our case, we propose an HPP layer composed of 2D convolutional layers that compress and summarize the spatial information to extract better features than just using non-trainable mathematical operations. This way, for a given input of shape $w \times h \times c$, our HPP extracts a set of P feature vectors (as many as pyramidal splits) composed each one of D features. After that, a trainable Attention Mask is applied to scale the importance of the P feature vectors. In this way, the model can pay more attention to those pyramidal features that better describe the gait, reducing the amount of noise included in the final descriptors. Note that, in this case, we apply Eq. 3 where x is the input data, AM_i is the attention mask for a given region x_i and $N = P$ is the number of regions, which is equal to the number of pyramidal splits. Finally, all descriptors are concatenated to produce a global feature vector.

$$SAHPP(x) = \text{concat}(\text{conv2D}_i(AM_i \cdot x_i)), \quad 1 \leq i \leq P \quad (3)$$

where x is the input data, P is the number of pyramidal regions and AM_i is the attention mask for a given region x_i .

Temporal Attention HPP. To produce richer features, we propose a second HPP layer to include the temporal information in the training process and attention mechanism. In this case, the structure of the layer is similar to the Spatial version but using 3D convolutions as shown in Eq. 4. Therefore, the produced features

include a mixture of spatial and temporal information. Again, after the HPP, we attach a trainable Attention Mask to weigh the importance of each pyramidal feature.

$$TAHPP(x) = \text{concat}(\text{conv3}D_i(AM_i \cdot x_i)), \quad 1 \leq i \leq P \quad (4)$$

where x is the input data, P is the number of pyramidal regions and AM_i is the attention mask for a given region x_i .

3.2. Training process

We use the well-known Triplet and Crossentropy losses to train AttenGait and classify the human identities (Fig. 2). In order to improve the performance of the approach, we append a Triplet loss and a Crossentropy loss to each pyramidal feature produced by the *common branch*. This way, each final loss is computed as the average among all pyramidal parts. Since the identification process (Sec. 3.3) is carried out with a Nearest Neighbour classifier, the last epochs are performed using only Triplet loss to reduce the noise produced by the Crossentropy loss.

To deal with different temporal positions in a sequence, samples with random starting points are used during training. Specifically, from each input sequence of T frames, we build subsamples taking L contiguous frames, being $L \leq N$ and randomly selecting the temporal position in T to start sampling the L frames for each mini-batch used during training. Thus, depending on the starting position, we can generate different subsamples from each original video sequence.

3.3. Identification process

To avoid fine-tuning our models with test subjects, we use the model trained on the training subjects as a feature extractor to compute the gait signatures of

the test samples and classify them using a simple Nearest Neighbour (NN) classifier. Thus, we follow the typical protocol of gallery and probe sets used in other works [7, 9]. During test time, we use the whole sequence as input instead of taking subsequences of L frames like during the training step.

4. Experiments

In this section, we present experimental results with AttenGait. First, we present the datasets and metrics used in our experiments (Sec. 4.1). After that, we provide some implementation details used in our approach (Sec. 4.2). Then, we report the experimental results of AttenGait using different modalities, and later, we compare it to the state-of-the-art (Sec. 4.4), together with an ablation study on the model (Sec. 4.5).

4.1. Datasets and metrics

We run our experiments on two of the largest public datasets for gait recognition: CASIA-B [12] and GREW [14]. Datasets that do not release the RGB images or the optical flow, as OU-MVLP [13], cannot be used in our experimental evaluation. We hope that the authors release them in the near future.

CASIA-B [12]. In this dataset, 124 subjects walk in an indoor environment while they are recorded from 11 viewpoints (*i.e.* from 0° to 180° in steps of 18°) with a video resolution of 320×240 pixels and 24 fps. Three walking conditions are considered: normal walking (*NM*), carrying a bag (*BG*), and wearing a coat (*CL*). In our experiments, we follow the experimental protocol defined in [18].

GREW [14]. This is the first large-scale dataset for gait recognition in the wild, composed of videos that contain hundreds of cameras and thousands of hours of

streams in open environments. The dataset includes 26,345 subjects and 128,671 sequences, 14,185,478 human boxes and a distractor set with 233,857 sequences. Moreover, it provides several modalities: silhouettes, Gait Energy Images (GEIs), optical flow, and 2D and 3D poses. In this case, we follow the experimental protocol explained in [14], and we provide the results obtained from Codalab ¹.

Metrics. To evaluate the system performance, we use the standard Rank-1 (R1) accuracy, *i.e.* the percentage of correctly classified videos: $R1 = \#correct/\#total$.

4.2. Implementation details.

Input data Following the recommendations of previous state-of-the-art works [7, 9], during training, we set the maximum temporal length of the input samples to $L = 30$ frames to reduce the memory requirements, while at test time, we use all frames. To reduce the computation, we resize the input data to 85×64 pixels, keeping the original aspect ratio. The unnecessary background is removed by cropping the frames to 64×64 , keeping the total height. Therefore, the shape of our input data is $64 \times 64 \times C \times L$ frames, where C is the number of channels of the input data and L refers to the number of frames of the sample, being $C = 2$ for optical flow (x and y components), $C = 1$ for silhouettes and gray images, and $C = 3$ for optical flow represented as RGB images, which is the optical flow included in GREW dataset.

In this paper, we use all visual modalities included in each dataset. This way, we use optical flow computed with Farneback [47], gray images, and silhouettes for CASIA-B. For GREW, we use optical flow represented as RGB images and

¹GREW test results: <https://codalab.lisn.upsaclay.fr/competitions/3409#results>

silhouettes. Therefore, AttenGait was tested on two datasets, three data modalities, and two different methods for obtaining the same modality (*i.e.* optical flow), demonstrating its robustness.

Architecture. AttenGait is inspired by the well-known architecture called Gait-Set, proposed in [6] but extended to make all layers trainable. Moreover, we use attention mechanisms inspired by visual transformers [16]. As shown in Fig. 2, our model is composed of a *main branch* with an initial convolutional layer (C1) followed by seven Attention convs (AC1, ..., AC7) with SiLU activation function, attention parameters $k_w = 3$ and $k_h = 3$, and a Max Pooling of 2×2 after AC3 and AC5. The details about each convolutional layer are defined as follows. C1: conv layer of 5×5 and 32 filters; AC1, AC2: 3×3 and 32 filters; AC3, AC4: 3×3 and 64 filters; AC5, AC6, AC7: 3×3 and 128 filters. For GREW dataset, we include two additional Attention convs after AC2, AC4, and AC6 using the same setup as its previous layer. The *Spatial Attention HPP* comprises five 2D convolutions (2D-C1, ..., 2D-C5) with kernel shape $d \times 16$ with SiLU. The *Temporal Attention HPP* is composed of five 3D convolutions (3D-C1, ..., 3D-C5) with kernel shape $d \times d \times 16$ with SiLU. For both cases d takes the following values: [1, 2, 4, 8, 16]. In this way, we build a trainable HPP based on convolutions with different kernel heights. Finally, to deal with different temporal lengths during test time, the exceeding temporal information is compressed using the sum of the mean and max values across the temporal axis as shown in Eq. 5.

$$G(\cdot) = \text{mean}(\cdot) + \text{max}(\cdot), \quad (5)$$

where $G(\cdot)$ are the summarized activations.

The last *common branch* is composed of two dense layers with 128 and 32 units per pyramidal partition, respectively. The final gait signature used to identify

the subjects has 1984 dimensions.

Hyperparameters. We implement AttenGait using Keras and TensorFlow 2.12. During training, we started from scratch using Adam with a minibatch of 64 samples for CASIA-B and 48 samples for GREW. To build our batch samples, we follow the $p \times k$ widely used strategy for Triplet loss, with $p = 8$ classes and $k = 8$ samples per class for CASIA-B. For GREW, we use $p = 12$ and $k = 4$. The learning rate starts at 0.001 and is reduced by 0.1 during the final fine-tuning (see below) using only Triplet loss. To avoid overfitting, we apply L2 regularization in all layers and dropout of 10% in the attention masks. The model is trained during 8000 epochs + 1000 fine-tuning epochs for CASIA-B and 2000 epochs + 500 epochs for GREW. For training CASIA-B, we use 2 NVIDIA A100 for eight hours and 8 NVIDIA A100 for seven days for GREW. To predict the identities of the subjects, we use a NN classifier with the gait signatures obtained from the last dense layer of the model.

4.3. Modalities comparison

In this experiment, we measure the impact of the different modalities on the final accuracy of AttenGait. Based on average accuracy, silhouettes obtain the lowest result, followed by gray/RGB images and optical flow. Tab. 1 summarizes the results for gray, RGB, silhouettes, and optical flow (OF) modalities on CASIA-B. These results make sense since silhouettes contain much less information than the other modalities. Focusing on gray and RGB images, both modalities achieve similar performance, although RGB encodes more information. In our opinion, RGB is not necessary for gait recognition since models need to get away from appearance details like clothes, body shape, hairstyle, etc., which are the details where colors play an important role. Therefore, using gray-scale images is more

<i>Modality</i>	<i>NM</i>	<i>BG</i>	<i>CL</i>	<i>Avg</i>
RGB	98.8	98.2	88.0	95.0
Gray	98.8	98.3	88.1	95.1
Silhouettes	95.1	90.5	71.3	85.6
OF	98.8	97.7	91.0	95.8

Table 1: **Modality study on CASIA-B**. Comparison between AttenGait models trained with different modalities. Each row represents a different modality. Each column represents a different scenario of CASIA-B. It is reported the Rank-1 accuracy (%) excluding identical-view cases. The best results are marked in bold.

<i>Modality</i>	<i>Rank-1</i>	<i>Rank-5</i>	<i>Rank-10</i>	<i>Rank-20</i>
Silhouettes	50.2	67.3	73.4	77.9
OF	70.7	82.9	86.9	89.2

Table 2: **Modality study on GREW**. Comparison between AttenGait models trained with different modalities. Each row represents a different modality. Each column represents a different Rank- n identification rate (%).

suitable and faster. Comparing optical flow and gray images, in that case, the most significant difference happens in the *CL* scenario where raw pixels can penalize the performance of the model due to the considerable differences in the visual appearance of the subjects due to changes in the clothes. This way, optical flow is less penalized by those changes and can achieve better results than raw pixels.

The results of the GREW dataset (Tab. 2) show the same behaviour identified in CASIA-B. Note that in this case, only optical flow and silhouettes are available. As expected, optical flow achieves the best results for all Rank- n , showing the benefits of using better modalities with richer information. Silhouettes obtain lower results than the other modalities but better than well-known silhouette-based state-of-the-art approaches like GaitSet [6] or GaitPart [7] (shown in Tab. 4).

4.4. State-of-the-art comparison

To put AttenGait results in context, we compare them with existing methods on two widely used datasets: CASIA-B and GREW. Note that our AttenGait results are obtained using optical flow as input.

CASIA-B.

Case	Method	0	18	36	54	72	90	108	126	144	162	180	Avg
NM	GaitGL [9]	96.0	98.3	99.0	97.9	96.9	95.4	97.0	98.9	99.3	98.8	94.0	97.4
	CSTL [48]	97.2	99.0	99.2	98.1	96.2	95.5	97.7	98.7	99.2	98.9	96.5	97.8
	<i>TransGait</i> [40]	97.3	99.6	99.7	99.0	97.1	95.4	97.4	99.1	99.6	98.9	95.8	98.1
	GaitStrip [39]	96.0	98.4	98.8	97.9	96.6	95.3	97.5	98.9	99.1	99.0	96.3	97.6
	GaitEdge [31]	97.2	99.1	99.2	98.3	97.3	95.5	97.1	99.4	99.3	98.5	96.4	97.9
	GaitGCI [49]	97.3	98.6	99.2	98.2	97.3	95.7	97.1	99.2	99.0	99.1	96.8	97.9
	GaitCoTr [42]	97.3	98.8	99.3	98.3	97.3	97.2	98.3	98.9	99.5	98.8	92.7	97.9
	DANet [50]	96.4	99.1	99.2	98.2	96.6	95.5	97.6	99.4	99.5	99.3	96.9	98.0
	<i>MMGaitFormer</i> [43]	98.1	98.6	99.0	98.1	98.4	97.8	98.1	99.0	99.2	99.1	97.3	98.4
	AttenGait-OF (ours)	98.4	98.2	98.6	98.1	98.7	99.0	98.9	99.2	99.3	99.3	99.3	98.8
	<i>AttenGaitOF+Gray (ours)</i>	99.2	99.2	99.1	99.2	98.8	99.0	99.2	99.4	99.3	99.2	98.9	<u>99.1</u>
	<i>AttenGaitOF+Sil (ours)</i>	99.1	99.1	99.2	99.2	98.6	98.7	99.1	99.3	99.1	99.4	99.4	<u>99.1</u>
	BG	GaitGL [9]	92.6	96.6	96.8	95.5	93.5	89.3	92.2	96.5	98.2	96.9	91.5
CSTL [48]		91.7	96.5	97.0	95.4	90.9	88.0	91.5	95.8	97.0	95.5	90.3	93.6
<i>TransGait</i> [40]		94.0	97.1	96.5	96.0	93.5	91.5	93.6	95.9	97.2	97.1	91.6	94.9
GaitStrip [39]		92.8	96.6	97.2	96.5	95.2	90.5	93.5	97.5	98.3	97.6	91.4	95.2
GaitEdge [31]		95.3	97.4	98.4	97.6	94.3	90.6	93.1	97.8	99.1	98.0	95.0	96.1
GaitGCI [49]		93.2	96.8	97.6	96.2	93.9	90.5	93.7	96.8	98.3	97.2	91.7	95.0
GaitCoTr [42]		87.7	98.4	97.8	96.0	94.7	92.1	93.7	96.5	97.7	97.5	92.5	95.0
DANet [50]		95.0	97.3	98.3	97.4	94.7	91.0	93.9	97.4	98.2	97.6	94.2	95.9
<i>MMGaitFormer</i> [43]		97.1	95.9	97.1	95.7	96.1	95.2	95.2	97.1	97.3	96.1	93.5	96.0
AttenGait-OF (ours)		96.9	97.9	98.3	98.2	97.2	95.4	97.2	98.7	98.8	98.6	97.4	97.7
<i>AttenGaitOF+Gray (ours)</i>		99.2	99.0	98.9	99.0	98.4	98.4	98.8	99.4	99.4	99.3	98.9	<u>99.0</u>
<i>AttenGaitOF+Sil (ours)</i>		98.1	98.5	99.1	98.4	96.6	96.0	97.9	99.0	99.2	99.1	99.2	98.3
CL		GaitGL [9]	76.6	90.0	90.3	87.1	84.5	79.0	84.1	87.0	87.3	84.4	69.5
	CSTL [48]	78.1	89.4	91.6	86.6	82.1	79.9	81.8	86.3	88.7	86.6	75.3	84.2
	<i>TransGait</i> [40]	80.1	89.3	91.0	89.1	84.7	83.3	85.6	87.5	88.2	88.8	76.6	85.8
	GaitStrip [39]	79.9	92.3	93.4	89.2	86.0	80.0	86.0	88.5	91.7	87.5	73.5	86.2
	GaitEdge [31]	84.3	92.8	94.3	92.2	84.6	83.0	83.0	87.5	87.4	85.9	75.0	86.4
	GaitGCI [49]	81.1	91.3	93.2	90.4	85.7	80.6	87.1	88.3	89.3	87.3	75.5	86.4
	GaitCoTr [42]	84.4	93.0	95.1	92.9	87.9	85.7	88.1	90.6	92.4	89.8	84.0	89.4
	DANet [50]	82.8	94.8	96.9	94.3	89.0	83.9	87.9	92.3	95.1	92.0	80.3	89.9
	<i>MMGaitFormer</i> [43]	93.9	98.0	96.9	96.0	93.7	91.6	93.5	96.4	96.5	95.7	90.2	94.8
	AttenGait-OF (ours)	91.1	95.3	96.0	95.3	89.9	88.4	89.5	91.3	88.8	89.4	86.0	91.0
	<i>AttenGaitOF+Gray (ours)</i>	96.0	97.0	97.7	97.3	94.6	92.9	93.0	94.8	91.1	91.4	88.6	94.0
	<i>AttenGaitOF+Sil (ours)</i>	92.8	95.5	95.8	94.2	91.6	88.8	91.1	92.8	91.2	92.0	87.4	92.1

Table 3: **State of the art on CASIA-B.** Rank-1 identification rate (%) excluding identical-view cases. The best single-modality results are marked in bold. The best multimodal results are underlined. Methods in italics use multiple modalities.

According to the results shown in Tab. 3, AttenGait obtains the best results for *NM*, *BG* and *CL* scenarios, achieving an average Rank-1 accuracy of 95.8% among

NM, *BG* and *CL* cases, while previous single modality state-of-the-art approaches like GaitGCI [49], GaitCoTr [42], and DANet [50] achieved 93.1%, 94.1%, and 94.6%, respectively. Comparing the results with the multimodal approach MM-GaitFormer [43], we achieve comparable results even though we use a single modality, and it only improves the *CL* scenario thanks to the multimodal setup. To perform a fair comparison, we propose a simple multimodal approach using a late fusion that performs a weighted sum [5] of each single modality model. Note that, we compute the L2 distance for each probe sample to all gallery samples, and then, we compute the inverse of those distances to obtain the probability distributions that are used for the late fusion. After thorough cross-validation, we have selected the weights [0.6, 0.4] for both combinations of modalities (OF+Gray and OF+Silhouettes). With both fusions, our results improve, and on average, we obtain the best multimodal results with 97.4% and 96.5% for OF+Gray and OF+Sil, respectively, while MMGaitFormer obtained 96.4%. Focusing on the different viewpoints, AttenGait obtains very stable results among cameras, without big drops in the accuracy for difficult cameras such as *0* or *180*, which are appreciated on other approaches. In our case, *NM* results are practically the same among cameras, oscillating by $\pm 0.5\%$ with respect to the average. Similar behavior is observed for *BG* where only the lateral view (*90*), which is one of the most affected by carrying objects, shows a drop of 2.3% with respect to the average. Finally, *CL* is the most challenging case since the subjects wear long coats and heavy clothes producing many occlusions depending on the viewpoint. Our results show more variations among cameras, especially in the back viewpoints (from *90* to *180*) with differences of up to 5% in the most challenging case with the camera *180*.

<i>Method</i>	<i>Rank-1</i>	<i>Rank-5</i>	<i>Rank-10</i>	<i>Rank-20</i>
GaitSet [6]	46.3	63.6	70.3	76.8
GaitPart [7]	44.0	60.6	67.3	73.5
GaitGL [9]	47.3	63.6	69.3	74.2
CSTL [48]	50.6	65.9	71.9	76.9
GaitCoTr [42]	55.6	70.9	76.2	80.4
TransGait [40]	56.3	72.7	78.1	82.5
GaitGCI [49]	68.5	80.8	84.9	87.7
AttenGait-OF (ours)	70.7	82.9	86.9	89.2

Table 4: **State of the art on GREW.** Rank- n identification rate (%). The best results are marked in bold.

GREW. AttenGait achieves the best results for all rank- n accuracies as shown in Tab. 4. Note that results for GaitSet and GaitPart are obtained from [14]. Since this dataset comprises many more samples than CASIA-B, our model can improve the state-of-the-art by a large margin. This is especially clear for Rank-1 accuracy, where AttenGait improves previous approaches by 2.2%. As the Rank level increases, accuracy improves but less than other approaches since our Rank-1 value is already noticeably higher than previous approaches.

4.5. Ablation study

In this section, we evaluate the behavior of AttenGait when different modifications are applied to the final model: *baseline*, *Spatial Attention HPP*, *Temporal Attention HPP*, and AttenGait without *final fine-tuning*. Note that in these experiments, for brevity, we present results only for CASIA-B and using optical flow as input. Results are obtained using a NN classifier. The final fine-tuning is applied only in the row ‘AttenGait’, which is our final version.

Baseline. Here, we train a model removing attention mechanisms, just keeping the convolutional and HPP layers without attention masks. Thus, the architecture

<i>Experiments</i>	<i>NM</i>	<i>BG</i>	<i>CL</i>	<i>Avg</i>
Baseline	98.2	95.3	82.3	91.9
Baseline w/ Attention+Spatial Attention HPP	98.6	97.6	88.8	95.0
Baseline w/ Attention+Temporal Attention HPP	98.7	97.4	89.9	95.3
AttenGait w/o ft	98.8	97.4	90.8	95.6
AttenGait	98.8	97.7	91.0	95.8

Table 5: **Ablation study on CASIA-B.** Comparison between the full AttenGait and different modifications. Each row represents a different version. Each column represents a different scenario of CASIA-B. The Rank-1 identification rate (%) is reported excluding identical-view cases.

is composed of the same blocks of Fig. 2 without attention masks. This can be considered as the baseline obtained with the basic version of AttenGait without attention mechanisms. Row ‘Baseline’ of Tab. 5 contains the results of this experiment. Comparing the average result with our final model (row ‘AttenGait w/o ft’), the contribution of our attention mechanism is clear, obtaining an average improvement of 3.7%. If we focus on the different scenarios, *CL* gets the highest boost in accuracy (8.5%) followed by ‘BG’ (2.1%), which shows the capabilities of our attention mechanism to deal with changes in the walking conditions.

Spatial Attention HPP. In this case, the architecture contains Attention Convs and the *Spatial Attention HPP*, removing the *Temporal Attention HPP*. The results of this experiment can be found in row ‘Baseline w/ Attention+Spatial Attention HPP’ of Tab. 5. Comparing the results with the Temporal Attention HPP (row ‘Baseline w/ Attention+Temporal Attention HPP’), the results are lower on average and for *NM* and *CL* scenarios. However, for the *BG* scenario, the model using only spatial information achieves better accuracy with an improvement of (0.2%). Therefore, spatial information allows the model to deal with small changes in

walking conditions like carrying bags.

Temporal Attention HPP. In this case, Attention Convs and *Temporal Attention HPP* are kept in the architecture to asses a different way of dealing with spatio-temporal information. Row ‘Baseline w/ Attention+Temporal Attention HPP’ of Tab. 5 contains the results of this experiment. In this case, the average results are better (0.3%) than the obtained by the Spatial Attention HPP (row ‘Baseline w/ Attention+Spatial Attention HPP’). Moving to the different scenarios, CL obtains a remarkable improvement of (1.1%) while the *NM* scenario obtains similar results. Thus, spatio-temporal information seems beneficial for difficult situations with extreme changes in the shape of the subjects.

AttenGait without fine-tuning. We evaluate the performance of applying the final version of AttenGait, including all modules but without the fine-tuning process explained above. Thus, this experiment allows us to measure the impact of having both Attention HPP modules simultaneously. The results of this experiment can be found in row ‘AttenGait w/o ft’ of Tab. 5. Comparing the results with the obtained using only a kind of Attention HPP (rows ‘Baseline w/ Attention+Spatial Attention HPP’ and ‘Baseline w/ Attention+Temporal Attention HPP’), this version improves all scenarios and the average accuracy, taking the best features from each kind of Attention HPP module to produce better gait signatures. Finally, if we include the fine-tuning process (row ‘AttenGait’), the final average accuracy is even better (95.8% vs 95.6%) like for *BG* (97.7% vs 97.4%) and *CL* (91.0% vs 90.8%) scenarios.

4.6. Understanding what AttenGait has learned

Using a model trained with optical flow on the 74 training subjects of CASIA-B, we want to understand what our model has learned. To this end, we apply two different visualization techniques that allow for studying the knowledge captured by the model. On the one hand, we use Grad-CAM heatmaps [51] to picture the regions of the input data with higher importance for the model in the AC7 layer. On the other hand, we use UMAP 2D projections [52] to plot the gait signatures of test subjects for all walking conditions and viewpoints.

Grad-CAM heatmaps. To use this visualization, the model must include a softmax classifier to produce a prediction from the input data. Thus, we use the model trained on the 74 training subjects and samples from the training set to display class activation maps. Note that we cannot use test subjects since our test model uses a NN classifier that does not produce a direct prediction from an isolated input sample. Fig. 4 shows three heatmaps for the same subject under three different walking conditions and viewpoints: (a) *NM* scenario and 0° camera, (b) *CL* scenario and 90° camera, and (c) *BG* scenario and 180° camera. In all cases, our model mainly focuses on the feet and arms of the subjects, ignoring the rest of the body. This behavior allows the model to focus on parts of the body that do not change between walking conditions like carrying a bag (*BG*) or wearing coats (*CL*), obtaining a better performance as shown in our experimental results.

UMAP projections. In this case, we use our test model that produces gait signatures of 1984 features since UMAP does not need any special requirement like Grad-CAM. We plot the UMAP 2D projections (using all default library parameters) of 10 test subjects for all test samples, including the three walking conditions and the 11 cameras. This way, we can visualize the robustness of the gait signa-

Figure 4: **Grad-CAM Activation heatmaps.** Visualization of three heatmaps obtained in the last Attention Conv (*AC7*) on CASIA-B using optical flow as input. **(a)** *NM* scenario and 0° camera. **(b)** *CL* scenario and 90° camera. **(c)** *BG* scenario and 180° camera. Note that warmer colors mean higher attention. (Best viewed in digital format)

tures produced by our model. Fig. 5 shows two different projections of the sample subjects and data. On the one hand, Fig. 5a has other markers for each walking condition and different colors for each subject (10 in total). Comparing the different walking conditions, *NM* and *BG* have very similar signatures, and both modalities are always overlapped. Regarding *CL*, depending on the subjects, the signatures are very similar (*e.g.* pink or dark blue subjects) or significantly different, being placed far from the rest of the samples belonging to the same subject (*e.g.* purple subject). This is the expected behavior according to the experimental results since *NM* and *BG* achieved top accuracies while *CL* scenario had lower results due to its difficulty. On the other hand, Fig. 5b has different markers for each viewpoint and different colors for each subject (10 in total). Comparing the different cameras, most of the samples are very close, building clear clusters of mixed cameras, showing the cross-view robustness of our model. However, in some cases, there are samples far from the cluster of the subject. Since those outliers belong to different cameras, we believe this is a collateral effect of the

Figure 5: **UMAP projection of gait signatures from 10 test subjects of CASIA-B.** (a) Colorized by subject id and marked by walking scenario. Samples include all viewpoints. (b) Colorized by subject id and marked by camera viewpoint. Samples include all walking scenarios. (Best viewed in digital format)

walking conditions and, specifically, of the *CL* scenario, as commented above.

5. Conclusions

We have introduced AttenGait, a novel neural network equipped with trainable attention mechanisms that allow the model to focus on the critical information of the gait. In contrast to previous state-of-the-art gait recognition approaches that rely on manual attention mechanisms, like horizontal cropping, our approach and its attention blocks are end-to-end trained to produce better gait signatures. Moreover, AttenGait is flexible and accepts different rich modalities such as optical flow or raw pixels. Most approaches focus just on silhouettes, which penalizes the learning capabilities of the model. In our case, we propose a bigger model with more trainable layers to take advantage of the richer input information. Thanks

to these two ideas (trainable attention and richer input data), AttenGait achieves state-of-the-art results on CASIA-B and GREW datasets.

However, although our attention modules are able to capture and give more importance to some parts of the input, their representation capabilities are limited to local spatial regions. This limitation can play an important role when there are drastic changes in the position or shape of the subjects. Therefore, as future work, we plan to investigate novel attention mechanisms to find and correlate sparse regions of the input to build more robust gait signatures. Moreover, we plan to investigate the performance of AttenGait by using multiple modalities simultaneously and the performance in other datasets that include human mesh information.

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